

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE COURSE OF MUSICAL-THEORETICAL DISCIPLINES

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Abstract: *innovative technologies in teaching provide not only the growth of knowledge, skills, abilities, skills, ways of activity and communication, but also reveal new possibilities of the personality of students. They are a necessary condition for the formation and improvement of value orientations through the inclusion of participants of the educational process in the meaningful experience of individual and collective activities as the accumulation of social experience, the adoption of criteria of social and professional success.*

Key words: *educational process, professional training of musicians, internal motivation, music-theoretical disciplines, innovative technologies.*

The main goal of educational activity should remain the formation of personality, maximally expressing the human potential. This leads to the increased importance of the higher education paradigm, which considers students as active, responsible and full-fledged subjects of educational activity, along with teachers. Conceptually, this paradigm aims at creating an educational space in universities that actively supports the intellectual and creative potential of students.

The problem of activation of students' cognitive activity is still one of the most topical in the theory and practice of higher professional education. Thus, recently the problem of using innovative teaching technologies in modern higher education institution is especially urgent. However, it should be remembered: in the process of modernization of the education system it is necessary to maintain an optimal balance between the introduced educational innovations and preservation of the best achievements of higher education.

Let's consider some educational technologies and the possibilities of their use in the course of such a musical-theoretical discipline as the analysis of musical works.¹

¹ Technologies and their essence are given in the work of Yu.V. Kit "Podgotovka rabotnikov sociokul'turnoj sfery: vybor pedagogicheskoy tekhnologii". M., 2015.

The technology of dialogue of cultures. This technology implies a through dialog of the speech element and the historical sequence of the main forms of European culture. This technology can and should be widely used when analyzing a work in a variety of situations: when considering the means of expressiveness of the work, when analyzing the form of the work, when listening to the work, finding out its dramaturgical laws, genre and style features, etc. Its essence consists in linking modern musical culture with the cultures of different epochs and peoples. Communicating with the student not on a business, but on a spiritual level, the teacher has a great opportunity to transfer knowledge to him, to form an attitude to music, art, culture, musician's activity and, what is no less important, improves himself.

The technology of problem-based learning implies a consistent and purposeful presentation of educational problems to students, solving which they actively assimilate knowledge. Obviously, knowledge should be given not in a ready-made form, but obtained in the process of independent cognitive activity in a problem situation. Thus, the process of cognition of students in this form of presentation of information is close to the search, research activity.

Problematic situations are those that can cause intellectual difficulties. The main forms of expressing the problematic are questions, cognitive tasks, educational assignments (independently select a piece of music for a specific form, compare the structure of several pieces with the same titles, but written by different composers, identify how the essence of the author's approach is manifested in the implementation of the idea, etc.). The effectiveness of this technology depends on the extent to which problem situations are used in the lesson.

Technology of developmental learning. The essence of this technology is the orientation of the educational process on the potentialities of each student, rather than on the program requirements. The analyzed work acts as an auxiliary didactic means to ensure further development of the student. Much attention can be paid to special preliminary analysis of individual expressive means, individual sections, and then the whole work in its entirety.

Computer technology involves the use of computer-based training and control programs. The following can be used in training: computer programs and music editors, computer tests, sounding of the orchestra without the soloist's part, information of educational and methodical character on CDs, etc.

In the conditions of increasing volumes of educational information, it is a priority to search for pedagogical means and technologies that allow to compress this information. Effective learning technologies of this kind include, for example, modular learning.

Modular learning emerged as an alternative to traditional learning. It integrates everything progressive that has been accumulated in pedagogical theory and practice in the field of pedagogical technologies. Thus, the idea of student's activity in the process of his clear actions in a certain logic, constant reinforcement of his actions by self-control, individualized pace of learning and cognitive activity is borrowed from programmed learning. Its very essence - the oriented basis of activity - is used from the theory of phased formation of mental actions. The reflexive approach is used from psychology.

The technology of modular learning creates a reliable basis for individual independent work of students and saving of study time without prejudice to the completeness and depth of the studied material. The student can work completely or almost independently with the individual training program offered to him/her, which includes: target lesson plan, information bank, methodological guidance on achieving the set didactic goals.

The functions of the teacher in this process are realized in the range from informational and advisory to controlling. In addition, flexibility and mobility in the formation of knowledge and skills of students is achieved, their creative and artistic thinking is developed. The positive point is that the next module, as a rule, is given after mastering the previous one. The completed module gives a complete picture of the level of development of certain qualities of the student. The module may contain assignments on various aspects. For example, a module may contain a specific set of assignments by blocks:

- to master the theoretical material on the topic (studying terms and concepts, getting into their essence), to get acquainted with a ready-made analysis of a musical example on the topic, to analyze a specific piece of music according to the teacher's proposed plan, to draw conclusions;
- self- study questions on the topic;
- homework, including not only tasks on the works studied, but also on the development of outlook and individual abilities of students.

Programmed learning technology involves the controlled assimilation of programmed learning material, which is a series of relatively small portions of educational information presented in a certain logical sequence. It is realized with the help of a learning device or a programmed textbook. For example, the student is developed and informed about the program of his/her development for a certain period and offered a list of books, audio and video recordings necessary for reading, given the methods developed by the teacher and applied in the analysis of a work, offered a list of works that the student should independently analyze.

Thus, the use of innovative methods of formation of modern professional competencies in students of higher education institutions of culture and art is designed not only to accelerate their entry into the global educational and cultural space, but also to improve the quality of education itself. Conducting classes, which are based on the intellectual dialog of the parties, contributes to increasing the role of the university in the system of higher education and cultural sphere - as an institution focused on training strategically thinking specialists capable of socially significant innovative transformations.

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